

A Study on Buying Behavior of Consumer towards Cosmetic Products in Jorhat City

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Abstract

The study is conducted from consumer buying behavior towards cosmetic products in Jorhat City. 120 samples were taken from Jorhat city, Assam. Both Primary and secondary data were used in research. The data were collected with the help of interview schedule, which was later serially arranged coded, tabulated and statistically analyzed. Information on buying habits was depicted such as frequency and percentage. The Quality of cosmetic product is the major reason for the continuous purchase by the consumer using cosmetic products, quality, brand awareness, product knowledge, and price of the cosmetic products influenced by the age and occupation of the respondents. This study also contributes to the knowledge of how cosmetic companies will be able to understand buying habits of the consumers.

Keywords: Consumer Behavior, Cosmetic Products and buying habits.

1. INTRODUCTION

Consumer buying behavior is the sum total of a consumer's attitudes, preferences, intentions, and decisions regarding the consumer's behavior in the marketplace when purchasing a product or service. The Indian cosmetic industry has witnessed rapid growth over the last couple of decades. In that time the range of cosmetic and beauty products in India has widened tremendously. Indian competitors have begun to manufacture products to cater to an international need. New facts that have been reveal that the industry of cosmetic products in India is growing at an average rate of almost twenty percent annually, this increase is attributed to two main factors. The first being the increase for the demand in Indian cost-effective products and the second being the increased purchasing power of the average Indian. If marketer wants concrete positioning than the priority is to identify the consumers' buying behavior and marketer will be in better position to target that products and services to consumer. Buying behavior is focused towards the needs of individual, group and organization. So, requirement is to have proper understanding related to relevance of those needs with consumers buying behavior. It is important to determine the interaction of consumer with the marketing mix to understand the consumer buying behavior. The reason behind that is the psychology of each individual towards products and services differ according to the culture, attitude, past learning and perception. On the basis of that consumers make further decision regarding whether to purchase or not and from where to buy the product that the consumer prefers.

1.1. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the buying habits of college students in cosmetic products.
2. To find the effect of advertisement of cosmetic products on college students.
3. To identify the relationship between types of advertisement and buying habits.

1.2. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

During the course of study the following major limitations were observed,

- 1) The study will be limited to college of Jorhat district only.
- 2) The study will be limited to female respondents only.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology used in the study is as follow:

2.1. Sources of data:

The study is based on primary data & secondary data. Data has been collected through survey techniques with structured questionnaire.

2.2. Sample selected for the study:

A total of 120 respondents from Jorhat District were selected for the study. Multi Stage Random Sampling is used as research method.

2.3. Area of the study:

The study area is limited to Jorhat District in Assam.

2.4. Tools for analysis:

The statistical tool used for the purpose of the analysis of this study is simple percentage technique and ranking techniques. After the collection of data through the questionnaire, editing was done carefully. Based on the responses of the samples, tables were prepared.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Das and Pathak (1998) while studying buying habits of women consumers of Assam stated that consumer durables items were purchased by majority of families on cash basis. Fifty two per cent always checked the ISI mark while buying consumer durables. 72% always purchased consumer durables from reputed dealer and 96% always see warranty/guarantee cards.

Hanzaee and Andervazh (2012) also reported that brand plays a major role while purchasing which is seen through the study on "The influence of brand loyalty on cosmetics purchase intention of Iranian female consumers" in which it was stated that there is positive and significant relationship between factors of brand loyalty with cosmetics purchase intention.

Vibhuti *et al.* (2014) found that 4 Ps of marketing that is price, place, promotion and product quality affect the consumer buying behavior along with psychological and physiological factors.

Desai (2014) in a study consumer buying behavior of cosmetic products in Kolhapur found that the major part of cosmetic market is covered by females. According to his research, quality is the most important factor influencing the consumer buying decision. Television and reference groups are other important factors to influence consumer buying decision. He also concluded that people are highly associated with the brand due to quality and results of the specific brand. Although people are becoming brand conscious but the actual brand decision is in their hands.

Nagananthi and Mahalakshmi (2016) Studied consumers' brand preference and buying behavior of cosmetic products at Coimbatore city. The main aim of study was to identify consumers' brand preference towards cosmetic products and to determine the relationship of brand factors with demographic data. They found that personal care is one of the most important reasons for purchasing cosmetics. Himalaya herbals were the most important brand among consumers. Demographic factors influence consumer to purchase the cosmetics.

In the study conducted by Rameshwari *et al.*, (2016) on "Consumer Buying Behavior of Cosmetic Products" observed that purchasing decision are taken by the consumers on their own, in spite of the impact of friends, family members, beauticians and others. Regarding the place of purchase it was reported that majority of respondents preferred to purchase products from permanent stores, private bazaars and medical shops as they feel it was easily available and products are of good quality.

Khan *et al.* (2017) studied men's attitude and motivation towards consumption of grooming products: A comparison of Chinese and Pakistani male consumers and they found that physical attractiveness is the most important factor for Pakistani males while Lifestyle is the most important factor for Chinese males for selecting grooming products. In another study of male consumers among teenage boys in Wayanad district of Kerala stated that men's cosmetics purchasing behaviors are strongly influenced by cultural and personal factors. Although the relatively higher average reflected their positive attitudes towards the purchase of cosmetics, they still maintain traditional consumption behaviors (Rafeeqe, 2015).

Bhatt and Sankhla (2017) also reported in their study on the consumer buying behavior towards cosmetics in Gujarat that people consider quality as the most important factor to purchase cosmetics. Rameshwari *et al.* (2016) also reported the same that quality was found as a most important factor for purchase of cosmetics by the respondents than price. It is also found that the use of internet by students and highly education consumers are also emerging as important factor.

Anjana and Vidyapeetham (2018) reported that mainly five factors, quality product, product price, brand name, product packaging and advertising have greater impact on customer purchasing decision, they also reveal that Brand, Quality and price are one among the strong competing factors in the decision making process.

• STAGES IN THE BUYING PROCESS

According to Philip Kotler, the typical buying process involves five stages the consumer passes through as described below:

The Consumer Buying Process

Fig: Consumer Buying Process

1. Problem Identification

This step is also known as recognizing of unmet need. The need is a source or force of buying behaviour. Buying problem arises only when there is unmet need or problem is recognized. Need or problem impels an individual to act or to buy the product.

2. Information Search

Interested consumer will try to seek information through newspapers and magazines, watch television, visit showroom or dealer, contact salesman, discuss with friends and relatives, and try all the possible sources of information.

3. Evaluation of Alternatives

Consumers evaluate competitive brands to judge which one is the best, the most attractive. Evaluation calls for evaluating various alternatives with certain choice criteria.

4. Purchase Decision

This is the stage when the consumer prefers one, the most promising brand, out of several brands. The former stage helps consumers evaluate various brands in the choice set. The brand that offers maximum benefits or satisfaction is preferred.

5. Post Purchase Decision

Consumer buys the product with certain expectations. Though he decides very systematically, there is no guarantee of a complete satisfaction. There is always possibility of variation between the expected level of satisfaction and the actual satisfaction. His subsequent behavior is influenced by degree of satisfaction/dissatisfaction.

4. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Sl.No.	Statements	Always (4)		Sometimes (3)		Rarely (2)		Never (1)		Wt. Score	Mean Score	Rank
		(f)	(%)	(f)	(%)	(f)	(%)	(f)	(%)			
1.	Checking the quality of cosmetic products.	93	77.5	16	13.33	6	5	5	4.16	437	3.64	I
2.	Checking the manufacturing/ expiry date.	89	74.16	16	13.33	10	8.33	5	4.16	429	3.57	II
3.	Reading the label thoroughly.	83	69.16	22	18.33	10	8.33	5	4.16	423	3.52	III
4.	Change the opinion about the product after watching the advertisements.	75	62.5	33	27.5	9	7.5	3	2.5	420	3.5	IV
5.	Checking the information of the product.	86	71.16	16	13.33	9	7.5	9	7.5	419	3.49	V
6.	Purchase cosmetics as per your skin type.	78	65	28	23.33	4	3.33	10	8.33	414	3.45	VI
7.	Going to a particular shop.	64	53.33	50	41.66	0	0	7	5.83	413	3.44	VII
8.	Look for the seal of the product.	69	57.5	27	22.5	19	15.83	5	4.16	400	3.33	VIII
9	Buying a particular brand of cosmetic product.	64	53.33	36	30	12	10	8	6.66	396	3.3	IX

10.	Checking of the price written on the label.	65	54.16	32	26.66	15	12.5	8	6.66	394	3.28	X
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Table: Buying habits of the respondent:

From the further analysis of data presented in Table it can be concluded that the habit of checking the quality of cosmetic product was ranked I followed by checking of expiry/manufacturing date (rank II) and reading the label thoroughly was (ranked III). The least Checking of the price written on the label was (ranked X).

- **FINDINGS:**

- ❖ From the further analysis of data presented in Table it can be concluded that the habit of checking the quality of cosmetic product was ranked I followed by checking of expiry/manufacturing date (rank II) and reading the label thoroughly was (ranked III). It may be because now a day's every person is conscious about reading label of any product.
- ❖ Change the opinion about the product after watching advertisement was (ranked IV), it may be because through advertisement people comes to know about different new products very easily.
- ❖ Checking the information of the product was (ranked V).
- ❖ Purchase cosmetic product as per your skin type was (ranked VI), it may be because now a day's maximum people specially females facing lots of skin problem so they more liked to purchase cosmetics according to their skin.
- ❖ Going to a particular shop (ranked VII) because females think that it is easy and safe for purchase the cosmetic products.
- ❖ Look for the seal of the product was (ranked VIII).
- ❖ Buying a particular brand of cosmetic product was (ranked IX) it may be because day by day females have become more brands loyal in cosmetics.
- ❖ Checking of the price written on the label was (ranked X).

5. CONCLUSION:

As cosmetic industry in India is one of the growing industries, marketers should know about the factors affecting purchase decision along with the attitude, perception and learning habits of consumer towards cosmetics. The Study shows that people always consider quality as the most important factor while purchasing cosmetics and they also consider the advice of beautician. People consider cosmetics as necessary part of routine life which is positive insight for marketers of cosmetic product.

- **SUGGESTIONS:**

The study can be helpful for the marketers to understand what triggers a consumer's interest to purchase cosmetic products.

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